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The number of articles dealing with metrics grows faster than the Web of Science itself

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Introduction

In this contribution, we want to show the evolution of the most-used terms referring to the field of bibliometrics (used here in a broad sense). As similar studies have been done in the past, see e.g. (Hood and Wilson, 2001; Mejia et al., 2021), this paper can be considered a partial update.

Articles referring to the field of bibliometrics have been assigned to different categories and have made use of several keywords over the years: bibliometrics, scientometrics, informetrics, webometrics and webmetrics, altmetrics or social media metrics; in addition, a small number of articles refer to cybermetrics, naukometrics, and librametrics.

Besides showing the evolution in the use of the “metrics” terms in absolute numbers, we also want to find out their relative use, answering, for instance, questions such as “which term is the most-used metric term”, “which term(s) show an increasing use with respect to the other terms” and most importantly “is the relative number of publications using metric terms increasing or decreasing with respect to the whole database”. We performed these investigations in two databases (WoS and Scopus) but, due to lack of space, we only report on the results obtained from the WoS.

Data collection

We collected data in the Web of Science Core Collection (WoS), and Scopus on March 22, 2022, performing queries related to the following terms:

bibliometr*

(scientometr* OR naukometr*)

(informetr* OR infometr*)

(webmetr* OR webometr* OR cybermetr*)

(altmetr* OR “social media metr*”)

For completeness' sake we also searched for librametr* but it turned out that this term is rarely used, mostly by Indian colleagues (the term has been proposed by Ranganathan) or by colleagues, like us, who try to cover all possible metric terms.

Moreover, we collected the data for the union of the resulting sets related to these metrics. We recall that it is not possible to search for 'metrics' as this term is also used in computer science. On the one hand, we consider the term infometrics as an error (the term should not be used), but on the other hand, we consider the terms webometrics and webmetrics as equally valid, be it that webometrics is the original term (Almind & Ingwersen, 1997), while personally, we prefer the term webmetrics.

These searches were restricted to the period 1955-2021 and were performed for all fields, (ALL=) hence including e.g., the journal *Scientometrics*), as a topic search (TS=), and as a title search (TI=). Finally, we also performed a topic search, restricted (by 'analyzing') to the WoS category of Information science and library science. The difference between an (ALL=)-search and a (TS=)-search is discussed in (Fassin & Rousseau, 2022).

We also searched for the term "science of science" because it precedes the formal introduction (or practically coincides with it, in the case of bibliometrics) of the other terms.

Similar to the searches in the WoS, we performed searches in Scopus but we will discuss the results (largely similar) in another paper.

Global results and a short discussion of data obtained from the WoS

The following Table 1 shows the numbers of publications found by different searches in the WoS. Metric terms are represented by the most-important notion (so scientometrics stands for the results of e.g., TS= (scientometr* OR naukometr*).

Table 1. WoS results

	ALL=	TS=	TI=	TS= (LIS)	ALL/TS	TS/TS(LIS)	TS/TI
Bibliometrics	20,564	20,250	8,740	5,375	1.02	3.77	2.32
Scientometrics	13,382	4,923	1,828	2,090	2.72	2.36	2.69
Informetrics	4,673	782	307	599	5.98	1.31	2.55
Web(o)metrics	889	585	149	376	1.52	1.56	3.93
Altmetrics	1,430	1,327	539	633	1.08	2.10	2.46
Librametrics	7	7	3	7	1.00	1.00	2.33
All metrics	32,488	25,014	11,357	7,656	1.30	3.27	2.20
Science of science	557	347	130	71	1.61	4.89	2.67

Table 1 shows that among the metrics terms bibliometrics is the most used, say most popular, one, followed by scientometrics. Yet, because there exists a journal *Scientometrics*, and not a journal called Bibliometrics (at least not in the WoS) the difference between the use of these two terms is much smaller for ALL= than for TS=. The terms webmetrics (and variants), "science of science" and the Indian term librametrics are the least popular. Because of the extremely low numbers, we exclude the term 'librametrics' from further discussion. The fifth column, i.e., the ratio between the second and the third column, reflects the influence of the journals *Scientometrics* and *Informetrics* and of the biennial conferences of the ISSI (International Society for Informetrics and Scientometrics) on the use of these terms.

Restricting TI= to LIS for all metrics yields 3,156 items, less than half of the TS= search. Finally, the sixth column indicates the relative importance of these metric terms in the field of Information and Library Science. Here we see that informetrics and webmetrics are the most typical terms (the least dispersed to other fields) for the LIS field. Bibliometrics and certainly “science of science” are, relatively speaking, the best known outside our field. The ratio TS/TI is calculated to answer the question “If the term is used, is it then mentioned in the title?” Values (ratios) here are similar for all metric terms, except for the term webmetrics which is not so often used in the title.

We also collected the timelines for each (TS=) search. These are discussed further on. Remarkably, informetrics and webmetrics reached their top (absolute numbers) already a few years ago.

Bibliometrics vs. scientometrics

The use of the terms scientometrics (starting in 1976) and bibliometrics (starting in 1969, which is the year in which (Pritchard, 1969) proposed the term) both show a steep increase in their absolute use, see Figs. 1-2. We recall that the term bibliometrics was introduced by Otlet (1934), but this was largely forgotten by 1969. The term naukometriya = scientometrics was introduced by Nalimov in the Russian literature in 1966 (Nalimov, 1966) and made popular first as a Russian term (Nalimov & Mul’chenko, 1969), and later through its translation as scientometrics, see (Rousseau, 2021) for more details on the history of this term.

Figure 1. Timeline TS=bibliometr*

Figure 3, using a 3-year moving average, shows the relation between scientometrics and bibliometrics over time (starting in 1980). Clearly, bibliometrics has always been the more popular one. Its relative use with respect to scientometrics has been increasing, especially since the year 2000, leading to a decreasing trend line for (use of scientometrics)/(use of bibliometrics).

Informetrics

The next figure (Figure 4) shows the use of the term informetrics. Here we see a clear increasing trend. The first occurrence of this term was in 1979, the year in which the term has been proposed.

Figure 2. Timeline TS=(scientometr* OR naukometr*)

Figure 3. Use of the term scientometrics versus use of the term bibliometrics

Webmetrics

The use of the term web(o)metrics begins in 1997, the year in which the term was introduced by Almind and Ingwersen (Almind & Ingwersen, 1997). It shows an increasing trend until 2018 but seems on the decline since then, see Figure 5.

Figure 4. Timeline for TS = (informetr* OR infometr*)

Figure 5. Timeline for TS= (webmetr* OR webometr* OR cybermetr*)

Altmetrics

The first use of the notion of altmetrics occurred in 2005 as “social media metrics”. The term altmetrics itself was proposed by Priem et al. (2010) in 2010, but it is only since 2014 that the use of this term became increasingly popular, see Figure 6.

Figure 6. Timeline for TS=(altmetr* OR “social media metr*”)

All metric terms

Bringing all “metrics” together we see (Figure 7) that there is a huge increase, driven by the term bibliometrics and scientometrics, mainly since the year 2005.

Figure 7. Timeline for all metrics terms

This is a very important result showing the growth – with respect to all topics - in the relative importance of quantitative methods (metrics) to study researchers, research results, and science itself.

Figure 8. Relative increase of the “metric” terms

Discussion

Is it possible to define the practical difference between bibliometrics and scientometrics?

In earlier publications colleagues tried to define and delineate the difference between the metric terms, see e.g., (Ingwersen & Björneborn, 2004) including their famous Figure 15.1, but nowadays we consider it futile to try to find out the difference in use (and hence in meaning) between bibliometrics, scientometrics, and informetrics; and aren't most metric investigations in some way web-related? For this reason, we do not try to formulate an exact definition for the different metric terms. Obviously, to cover all metric fields one must search for all terms.

Articles on scientometrics before the launch of the journal Scientometrics

We found five articles using the term scientometrics (but not naukometriya), all published in 1976, published before the launching of the journal *Scientometrics* (in 1978), among which two by Derek de Solla Price, published in the *International Forum on Information and Documentation*.

The influence of journals on search results

The following Figure 9 shows the timelines for the number of publications obtained by the search ALL= (scientometr* OR naukometr*) and the number of publications in the journal *Scientometrics* (WoS data). Clearly, in the earlier years, the two almost coincide, while there is a marked difference between them since about the year 2005. In later years the influence of the proceedings of the biennial conference of the International Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics (ISSI), published under different names, becomes very clear in the results for the (ALL=)-query.

Figure 9. Scientometrics and the influence of the journal with the same name

The difference between (ALL=) and (TS=)-queries

Comparing our timelines with those shown in Mejia et al. (2021) we first notice that Mejia et al. only show the part between 2011 and 2020. More importantly, according to their timelines in 2013, the use of the terms bibliometrics and scientometrics is almost equal (in the WoS Core Collection), while this does not show at all in our Figure 3. Checking, we found that Mejia et al. did not do a (TS=)-query, but an (ALL=)-query. This was not clear from their explanation. Moreover, a (TS=) query refers to the use of these terms by scientists in their articles, while an (ALL=) refers to the use of the metric terms over the whole database, including their use in journal titles, conferences, and books. Both points of view are valid of course. With a (TS=)-search one misses some implicit uses of the terms, as all articles published in journals such as *Scientometrics* and the *Journal of Informetrics* can be assumed to deal with metric-related topics. Yet, an article published in the *Journal of Informetrics* may deal exclusively with a webmetric or altmetric topic, or may only use the term bibliometrics in the body of the article, without mentioning it in the title, abstract, or keywords.

The curves for bibliometrics and scientometrics in the WoS have a clear “exponential-like” increasing trend. Yet, we know that such a trend cannot continue and at some point, the increase will slow down, leading to an S-curve. Yet, we have not yet reached the onset of an S-curve.

What we got and what we missed

When performing a bibliometric survey of a field it is important to assure that no “important” articles are missed. We first note that a search for the most popular term, namely ‘bibliometrics’ yielded 63% (ALL), 81% (TS), and 77% (TI) of all results (see Table 1). Combining bibliometrics and scientometrics via an OR-search yielded, respectively 92%, 93%, and 92% of all results. Would that suffice for some purposes? Checking what we missed, we found for the (TS)-query, 22 articles with more than 100 citations, among which 16 related to altmetrics and social media metrics, 3 related to webmetrics, and 3 related to informetrics. So, we would miss important contributions related to the newer subfields.

Conclusions and limitations

In this paper, we took a new look at the use of the metrics terms within the information sciences. Bibliometrics is the most used term to refer to quantitative studies of science.

Generally speaking, the use of all metric terms shows a huge increase, and this in absolute as well as relative terms. The term bibliometrics occurs in about 81% of the (TS=)-searches and in 63% of the (ALL=)-searches. As explained already, this lower percentage is because there is no journal in the WoS with the term “bibliometrics” in the title.

The most important observation is the fact that the growth in the use of metric terms is higher than the growth of the WoS, indicating an increasing interest in bibliometrics (in the broad sense).

It is important to check for complementary (even small) terms to be complete.

Limitations

An important caveat is the fact that the used databases only partially cover the Russian, Latin-American, Indian or Chinese literature, biasing this study in favour of use in the West. Moreover, we only studied publications. Hence, a more in-depth analysis should focus on the citation analysis of the metric fields.

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